

A critical study of Starhawk's *The Fifth Sacred Thing* in the perspective of Hindu Mythology

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Abstract:

This study examines *The Fifth Sacred Thing* penned by Starhawk, an American ecofeminist writer. This seminar work of Starhawk incorporates the elements of water, earth, air, and fire from nature, augmented by her chosen element, 'Love.' She strongly contends that these five elements (water, earth, air, fire) of nature, along with Love (her personal element), serve as breath and energy necessary for fostering a harmonious relationship between the community and nature. It will establish an emotional connection between humans and nature. She selected 'Love' as the fifth sacred element because of its association with forgiveness and its stronger resonance with women. Both 'earth' and 'love' are intertwined with the protagonist, Maya. This research notably connects the Starhawks' five fundamental principles with the 'Panchabhuta' of Hindu mythology. This paper also endeavors to illustrate how Madrone, a spiritual healer, grapples with her internal conflict between good and evil, as well as forgiveness and retribution, aligning with the divine methods of the Almighty, who may cleanse a corrupted civilization through the 'Second Coming.'

Keywords: Starhawk, Fifth Sacred Thing, Mythology, Love, Reshape.

This paper explores the historical context of Starhawk's *The Fifth Sacred Thing* (1993) with Hindu mythology. It elucidates the parallels and distinctions between the components of the novel and the 'Panchabhutas' of Hindu mythology, while also mirroring the concept of the 'Second Coming' of the Kalki avatar in Hinduism and the 'Messiah' in Christianity.

The novel should advocate for justice and ecological sustainability. *The Fifth Sacred Thing* by Starhawk is a dystopian novel. The text centers on a confrontation between the North, represented by San Francisco, and the South, represented by Los Angeles.⁽²⁾ Unlike other states experiencing anxiety and deprivation resulting from water scarcity. The northern populous, living in a harmonious and egalitarian society, does not face analogous challenges. All individuals should possess sufficient access to sustenance, hydration, and housing.

Miriam Simos (Starhawk) was born on June 17, 1951 in St. Paul, Minnesota. She is well known as a global activist and organizer. In total she penned twelve books including her classical works *The Spiral Dance* (1979), *The Fifth Sacred Thing* (1993), and *The*

Empowerment Manual : A Guide for collaborative Groups (2011) most of her works are modelled on earth-based spirituality and observation of nature. (Mirjalali, 3). As a feminist and humanitarian activist, she is a leading proponent of ecofeminism. She provided consultation for the documentaries *Goddess Remembered* and *The Burning Times*, directed by Donna Read and produced by the National Film Board of Canada, and co-authored the commentary for *Full Circle*, an upcoming film in the same *Women's Spirituality* series.

Starhawk creates two contrasting worlds in her novel. The North is a utopian society built by witches, where people of all races and creeds are sustainably living in harmony with nature. Astonishingly, it is a city where the shrines of Yemaya, Kuan Yin, and the Virgin Mary are equally honoured and prayed to by the citizens. Yemaya is an ancient goddess known as the queen of the sea in Yorubaland (modern Nigeria). She is worshipped as a goddess of home, fertility, love, and family. Like water, she embodies both change and constancy, bringing forth life, protecting it, and changing it as necessary. She reminds us that even the worst catastrophes can be endured and that, with her help, we can learn to negotiate the ebbs and flows of change in our lives⁽⁴⁾ with her wisdom, courage, and grace. The other goddess, Kuan Yin, is a Buddhist pantheon (Bodhisattva) from China and is the goddess of compassion, love, and sustainable harmony. The Virgin Mary, the mother of Jesus, is a figure of divine wisdom. Through this, Starhawk showcased a multicultural society where there are no battles or cultural conflicts. Here we can see the harmony of different cultures that come under one roof.

On the other side, we can see the opposite side of the same coin. It's a contrast world. In the South, an apocalyptic society (or dystopian society), which was created by millennia, is under military control. It is a city of hunger, poverty, and a natural resources-scarce society filled with inequalities and corruption.

As soon as the soldiers from the south knew about the utopian society in the north, they were astounded by the fact that it maintained a harmonious environment, which was something they had never even considered to be conceivable in their wildest aspirations. As an illustration of fantasy versus reality, good versus evil, and harmony versus discord, the novel written by Starhawk features a mixture of north and south that stand in stark contrast to one another. People are forced to reconsider the possibilities that are available to human willpower. where everything is possible with unity among ourselves.

The major aim of this paper is to focus on the five sacred things mentioned in the novel by Starhawk. They are water, earth, air, fire, and love. Here, we can observe the similarities between the 'Panchbhutas' mentioned in Hindu mythology and the five fundamental sacred things mentioned in the novel. According to Hindu mythology, the universe is made out of five causative factors. They are Jala (water), Prithvi (earth), Air (vayu), Agni (fire), and Akasha (sky). But here in the novel '*The Fifth Sacred Thing*,' Starhawk chose 'love' as her fifth sacred thing instead of Akasha (sky). Because it is through love and compassion that one can build a sustainable, harmonious society, water, earth, air, fire, and love are the things that no one can be denied.

Here 'love,' which is mentioned as the fifth sacred thing, is not only a love for one's family, one's community, one's region, or one's country. But it is a love and care that is related to every living and non-living thing existing in the universe. This kind of true and unconditional

'love' is only possible with the harmony in people with their fellow beings and the harmony in people with the nature they live in. The spiritual harmony that is interlaced between humans and their nature is the true fifth sacred thing (love). The Fifth Sacred Thing, 'love,' serves as a basis for the other four essential sacred elements: water, earth, air, and fire. The appropriate and sustained use of these four sacred entities was achieved only via the assistance of the fifth sacred entity. Valuing nature, honoring its existence, and safeguarding it for future generations is the most profound gift one can provide to the world to come.

“We hope for a harvest, we pray for rain, but nothing is certain. We say that the harvest will only be abundant if the crops are shared, that the rains will not come unless water is conserved and shared and respected. We believe we can continue to live and thrive only if we care for one another. This is the age of the Reaper, when we inherit five thousand years of postponed results, the fruits of our callousness toward the earth and toward other human beings. But at last we have come to understand that we are part of the earth, part of the air, the fire, and the water, as we are part of one another.” (Starhawk, 28)

The notion of panchabhutha is the most archaic instrument for analyzing the cosmos. It demonstrates their physical attributes. In Indian mythology, Prithvi (hardness), Jala (liquidity), Agni (heat and temperature), and Vayu (motion) are the foundational elements of creation, intricately associated with birth, life, death, and reincarnation, while also possessing spiritual connections to human health and destiny. Both 'The Fifth Sacred Thing' and panchabhutas represent a reverence for nature and the elements; nevertheless, they vary in their cultural interpretations and spiritual meaning. The novel's framework of five essential parts emphasizes ecology, social transformation, and communal strength. Both provide significant insights on how human cultures might coexist together and respect the sanctity of natural elements for a peaceful and sustainable cosmos, which embodies the 'love' upon which the whole world depends. The text is a significant addition to ecotopian literature and presents a compelling vision for an improved future.

Starhawk, in her novel, *The Fifth Sacred Thing*, seeks to strengthen women's ties to nature rather than weaken them, because she sees it as empowering for women. Starhawk first introduces her protagonist, Madrone, as she struggles to save the life of a feverish pregnant woman and her unborn child. Madrone's therapeutic approach is characterized by a profound connection to nature, as she states, "...she took a deep breath and repeated her own secret rhyme that took her quickly into a trance. Her body was like a tree with a hollow trunk; her roots could reach down to the great stores of ch'i in the molten mantle of the earth and bring it up." (Mirjalali, 7)

This paper has also laid emphasis on the common thread of portraying concepts of forgiveness vs. punishment present in 'The Second Coming' by W.B. Yeats, 'Kalki Avatar' in Hindu mythology, and 'Madron' in 'The Fifth Sacred Thing' by Starhawk. These exhibit similar kinds of themes like transformation, renewal, and the cyclical nature of existence with distinct spiritual, cultural, and environmentalist contexts.

Starhawk narrated in the novel should strive for justice and ecological balance to sustain freedom and the following of the Fifth Sacred Thing, 'Love'

"Love is all you need." The song played in her mind. But the Beatles misled us, she said to the air, thick with the ghosts of her own dead lovers. It wasn't all we needed. We wanted to love, freely and without barriers. We had to remake the world in order to do it."⁽¹⁾

Maya Greenwood, the protagonist of the novel, who is a creator of the ecotopian north community, is an independent, compassionate woman. Who has the supernatural capability to heal people by natural means. When the inhabitants of the South navigate to the North, the true challenges arise in her community. She becomes very impulsive and hardly stays still; she wants to be the destroyer to rend and tear with her nails, eat human flesh, and dance until the civilizations tumble under her feet.

She no longer wanted to discuss peace, harmony, and sustainability; instead, she sought to unleash thunderstorms, hurricanes, wildfires, and volcanic eruptions to devastate the community, with the intention of thereafter reconstructing it via her healing powers. The same impulsiveness, uncertainty, discord, and lack of reverence for humans and environment are evident throughout Hindu mythology. The transition from God's forgiveness to His retribution is exemplified in the notion of the 'Kalki Avatar,' in Hindu mythology. The Kali Yuga is known as the period of darkness and disaster. The Kali Era is a period designated for the restoration of justice and order. Kalki is a warrior akin to 'Maya' in The Fifth Sacred Thing, who emerged to vanquish malevolence and inaugurate a new epoch of tranquility and unity. Madrone started to enchat a mantra started resonating throughout her mind:

"When we are gone they will remain,
Wind and rock, fire and rain,
They will remain when we return,
The wind will blow and the fire will burn." (Starhawk, 61)

Maya, Kalki, and Messiah are three distinct characters who originate from different religions, communities, and time periods, yet they all share the common goal of restoring the cosmos. 'Messiah, of the Second Coming, and 'Kalki' of Hindu mythology have the spiritual and cosmic alignment to restore the old order with the new. It is in connection with the cosmic cycles of creation, destruction, and regeneration. Maya, in The Fifth Sacred Thing, is tasked with the transformation of a dismal society into a utopian one. But the three are travelling in the same way for the eternal cause in shaping the destiny of humanity and serve for the cyclical nature of existence and the enduring human quest for meaning, purpose, and transcendence in a world filled with turmoil and upheaval. The trio is instructing everyone to internalize spirituality via love and compassion, aiming to create a culture that inspires global harmony and fosters equity. In the fifth sacred thing, folks are not just degrading themselves and the system but also the very nature of which they are a portion. Starhawk laments the populace's ignorance on their complacent attitude towards nature. Nature is integral to our existence, just as we are integral to earth. We are an integral component of nature, akin to a fetus within its mother's womb, safeguarding their city from the annihilators, the women of the North, who constructed their city with the bricks of tranquility and the steadfast resolve of nonviolence, determined to violate their principles and inflict harm upon the destroyers with

their bloodthirsty claws. Maya, the architect and originator of the city, aspires to redefine the aspirations for her new realm.

Conclusion

The study investigated the significance and role of five sacred elements—water, earth, air, fire, and the fifth element, 'Love,' as identified by Starhawk in her novel *The Fifth Sacred Thing*—emphasizing the necessity of valuing and conserving nature for future generations to establish a sustainable and harmonious society. Starhawk emphasizes in her work the significance of love and compassion in cultivating peace and sustainability throughout society. Starhawk's novel also explored the concept of panchabhutha, the foundational elements of creation, and emphasized the significance of revering the nature. The author also prioritized five essential elements that emphasize ecology, social transformation, and communal strength, providing insights into how human cultures can cohabit and respect the sanctity of natural elements for a peaceful and sustainable cosmos.

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